

EDEN ISS

Quality Management Plan

prepared for

WP 1.1 – Administrative & Technical Management

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Executive summary

This document establishes the quality assurance strategy to assure that adequate quality standards are defined and observed within the EDEN ISS project such that all deliverable products comply with the agreed project requirements and specifications.

The present document is applicable to all contributing partner organizations and contractors within this project.

This plan will be augmented on the contractor side by dedicated Product Assurance (QM) plans (if applicable) and organizations compliant to the requirement of the plan. This document addresses all phases of the development and qualification.

Nomenclature: Within the framework of European Cooperation for Space Standardization (ECSS) the term “Product Assurance” is used as the common ground for the quality management aspects (this document) and the technical aspects related the risks and their reduction. Where appropriate this term is also used in the present document.

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Acronyms

Acronym	Explanation
AIV	Assembly, Integration, Verification
ADP	Acceptance Data Package
ADS	For Airbus Defense and Space
AIT	Assembly, Integration and Test
AS	Aero Sekur S.p.A.
AWI	Alfred-Wegener-Institut
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
DCL	Declared Components List (EEE Parts List)
DLO	Stichting Dienst Landbouwkundig Onderzoek
DLR	Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt
ECP	Engineering Change Proposals
ECSS	European Cooperation for Space Standardization
EDEN ISS	H2020 Project (our project! ☺)
EEE (parts)	Electronic, Electrical, Electromechanical (parts)
ES	EnginSoft S.p.A.
ESA	European Space Agency
FDIR	Fault Detection, Isolation and Recovery
FMECA	Failure Modes, Effects and Criticality Analysis
H/W or HW	Hardware
HS	Heliospectra AB
LIT	Limerick Institute of Technology
LSG	LIQUIFER Systems Group GmbH
MTF	Mobile Test Facility
NCR	Non-Conformance Report (Problem Report)
NCR	Non Conformance Report
QM	Product Assurance
PMP	Parts, Materials and Processes
RfW	Request for Waiver
S/W or SW	Software
SOM	Software Operation Manual
TASI	Thales Alenia Space Italia S.p.A.
TB	Technical Board
TPZ	Telespazio S.p.A.
UoG	University of Guelph
QM	Quality Management

1 General

1.1 Quality Management Objectives

The EDEN ISS Quality Management (QM) program shall ensure that:

- any potential risk conditions are identified as early as possible and are appropriately addressed within risk control measures. In most cases it will be sufficient to apply normal engineering expertise instead of complex software based tools
- no failure within the EDEN ISS component can propagate into higher level systems
- the maximum project success expectance is achieved and
- no safety risk is created at any phase of the operations incl. testing and integration – this includes labour safety as well.

Since at least in the present project phase no hardware items will be produced which will actually be operated in the space environment, the following will apply to the QM program:

- the selection of parts, materials and processes will be performed according to flight standards only as far as necessary and affordable , which means:
 - flight-like equipment shall be selected when necessary to fulfill the on-ground demonstration objectives (i.e. for representativeness of material bio-contamination) or in view of future upgrade into a flight demo (i.e. achieving ISPR system fit and function, to avoid interface issues of flight demo)
 - Flight certification/control levels are not necessary for flight-like equipment
- no reliability and FDIR analyses are required
- the actions needed to upgrade the key system/subsystems to assure additional safety constraints of space flight (i.e. ISS environment for ISPR) will be highlighted, to be implemented with the same logic of the selection of parts, materials and processes described above.

Nevertheless, quality assurance means like inspection and pre-/post-test reviews shall be implemented (if needed) in order that the produced or procured hardware/software complies with agreed standards/specifications and that tests are performed such that the results could be repeated if necessary and can be assessed e.g. for completeness of the test results. In this frame also the configuration of produced/procured items must be defined and monitored e.g. in order to assure traceability of the development and the test results.

The QM program will start in the development phase and shall be effective in all following project phases, as applicable.

1.2 QM/Quality Assurance Organization within the EDEN ISS Project

The Product/Quality Assurance (QM) tasks within EDEN ISS are planned, coordinated and implemented by a dedicated QM Manager for the EDEN ISS project. The QM manager has access to central DLR services in the field of QM (e.g. reliability analysis).

The QM manager responsibly plans the overall QM program and the specific tasks to be executed (Quality Management Plan, this document). During the project phases they co-ordinate and monitor

the execution of the QM/Quality Assurance program. They also manage the fulfilment of the tasks for other DLR sites, project partners and industrial members of the EDEN ISS project. The specifics of the QM organization of the project are defined in Table 1-1.

Table 1-1: QM Responsibilities

Organisation	QM Responsible	Task
DLR Bremen	Vincent Vrakking (vincent.vrakking@dlr.de)	Main Coordinator
DLR Bremen	Dr. Matthew Bamsey (matthew.bamsey@dlr.de)	Support
DLR Bremen	Dr. Johannes Rößler (Johannes.roessler@dlr.de)	Consultant on DLR site
DLR Bremen	Catherin Hobbie (Catherin.Hobbie@dlr.de)	Consultant on DLR site

1.3 Responsibilities

The EDEN ISS QM/Quality Assurance manager is responsible for:

- QM organization
 - Planning
 - Surveillance
 - Reporting
- Risk Management (risk identification, tracking, close-out)
- Quality Assurance
 - Performance of inspections (only if necessary)
 - Support to the AIV process incl. tracking of requirements
 - Support to test conductance (test readiness and optional post-test reviews)
- Safety Assurance
 - Prepare safety analysis
 - Prepare safety data package
- Configuration Control
 - Surveillance (configuration inspections, if needed)
 - Prepare and maintain status lists
 - Hardware QM and Software QM
 - Documentation
 - Maintain and monitor change processing
 - Non-conformances tracking
 - Engineering Change Proposals (ECP)
 - Requests for Waiver (RfW), if applicable.

1.4 Personnel Training and Certification

The DLR RY has a dedicated program for training and (re-) certification. At DLR, training on the intent and application of the ECSS system and the EDEN ISS QM program will be provided to the relevant engineering and management personal (if needed). Additional training requirements are defined in the further course of the project e.g. considering specific process related capabilities.

1.5 Contractor and Supplier Surveillance

The EDEN ISS QM program will be applicable to all contributors of EDEN ISS subsystems and scientific instruments. During the development phase this will be accomplished by review and discussion of specifications and drawings. During the subsystem development phase the QM program will be implemented by inspections of critical steps performed by the EDEN ISS /Project QM at the contributors premises (if needed). The QM tasks which need to be delegated will be coordinated by the EDEN ISS project QM.

1.6 Status Reviews

The EDEN ISS/ project QM will contribute to and participate in the EDEN ISS project milestone reviews. The coordination will be done by the EDEN ISS /Project QM responsible. In particular, the following will be ensured:

- General status
- Status of risk assessment, especially progress of mitigation action items
- Status of Parts, Materials, Processes (PMP) procurement
- Response to action items of previous reviews
- Problem areas

During the H/W development phase of the project, monthly teleconferences will be organized in order to track the status of the different developments. In addition, all WP leaders will have to deliver monthly status reports, which will also be discussed and reviewed during these monthly meetings. During this phase, the EDEN ISS QM and the coordination team will have regular (once a month) product assurance meetings to review these open items and to address all open issues and challenges.

2 Quality Assurance

2.1 Tasks

The quality assurance tasks for the EDEN ISS consortium mainly are:

- Performance of quality control inspections especially configuration verification as part of tests (if applicable)
- Participation in the establishment and the review process of test specifications, test procedures, test reports and surveillance of the test program including monitoring of the re-test program
- Generation and/or processing of non-conformance reports
- Subsystem acceptance
- Acceptance data package preparation.

During the AIT phase of the Mobile Test Facility (MTF), dedicated subsystem personnel from the responsible partners will be sent to DLR (Bremen) in order to assist with the integration and test of the subsystem into the overall system.

2.2 Incoming Inspections

Incoming inspections will mainly be performed for all incoming parts, raw materials and sub-units which are delivered by partners and sub-contractors respectively, which are procured from industrial suppliers. The partners are obliged to perform incoming inspections for all procured parts, materials and sub-units according to the project specific incoming inspection procedure or an in-house equivalent. It shall be assured that all incoming items comply with the relevant design respectively procurement specifications. Dedicated incoming inspection protocols will be established before the actual inspection takes place in order to assure that all relevant inspection aspects are reflected in the procedure and that the applicable system specification requirements are fulfilled.

The incoming inspections will mainly assure that the delivered hardware is:

- In compliance with the relevant (especially interface) specification
- Any applicable legal safety requirements are met
- Suitably packed
- Complete and thoroughly tested
- All open activities are clearly identified and are acceptable for deferring to the next higher integration level
- All necessary precautions and warnings for the integration are completely defined and understood
- Free from obvious damages
- Visibly clean
- Adequately labelled
- Necessary protection devices are installed

- Adequately documented, especially that the ADP (Acceptance Data Package) (resp. equivalent delivery documentation) is complete.

If hardware, which is delivered for AIT purposes, and which is not working or does not conform to the specifications, the consortium partner in charge for the hardware is responsible either to come to DLR site to fix the hardware or to aid in the resolution the problem remotely.

2.3 Logbooks, Traceability & Acceptance Data Package (ADP)

Each partner shall maintain logbooks to record all major AIT activities related to the EDEN ISS Systems. Similarly, on system level the AIT, final close-out and shipment activities shall be recorded. The logbooks will be delivered to higher level integration to keep track of the further actions. In addition, the following logbooks shall be kept on system as well as on subsystem level:

- Log of temporary installed items
- List of deferred/open work.

The logbooks shall become part of the ADP and shall accompany the hardware through the next test and integration levels. Furthermore, the ADP shall be delivered together with the hardware item. The ADP comprises the following documents/ information:

- Configuration items & Part lists (incl. spare-, test- parts)
- Material list
- Design and configuration drawings
 - Mechanical (overview) drawing
 - Electrical (overview) drawing
- General user manual (if applicable)
- AIT instructions
- Maintenance procedures
- Dedicated tools for AIT procedures
- Safety instructions

In case of software delivery, the following additional information shall be included into the ADP:

- Software Operation Manual (SOM)
- Test procedures for Integrated tests on system level
- Install instructions & procedures

2.4 Handling, Storage, Packing, Marking and Labelling

Any equipment that is intended to be used for the Antarctic test campaign shall be stored under restricted conditions which are:

- Suitable environmental conditions (temperature, dust, humidity)
- Prevention of exchange with non-qualified materials
- Prevention from mechanical damage

- Prevention of biological decontamination (NOTE: In this sense no space-related strong regulations are meant (e.g. ExoMars requirements)). Rather general (obvious) precautions procedures are meant in order to deal with possible plant-related pathogen decontamination. This means:
 - Storage of H/W in a clean environment (e.g. seal-off container, plastic bag)
 - Cleaning of H/W prior to shipment with sanitizer (if applicable)

In addition, specific handling precautions will be reflected into integration procedures. DLR RY will supply (electronically) shipping labels and relevant packing slips to project partners to ensure commonality and consistency between EDEN ISS project related shipments.

3 Software Quality Assurance

3.1 Software Development Guideline

The present chapter describes the quality assurance techniques which will be applied to the software which is necessary to operate EDEN ISS cultivation systems and other important systems.

The software and hardware related performance shall always be treated in close correlation, especially on the system level. Special attention shall be paid to interface critical software. Special attention will also be put on the hardware software interaction with respect to clear task and interface definition.

The following baseline S/W design rules shall be considered:

- A modular architecture shall be implemented as a preferred solution
- The module size shall be as small as possible and about comparable for each module
- Failure tolerance shall be implemented at the lowest possible level
- The time-wise behavior of each module shall be predictable
- Potential malfunctions shall be testable.

The system robustness shall be assured by:

- Appropriate software handling of hardware malfunctions
- Avoidance of systematic software failures
- Avoidance of commanding errors
- Avoidance of insufficient synchronization of software and hardware processes.

A sufficient degree of failure tolerance shall be provided in the downloadable data set. A graphical overview on the software architecture including the hardware/software interfaces shall be provided.

Detailed design: The general and detailed software structure including all software modules, their internal and external interfaces are specified. The software code shall be commented. Each change shall be indicated.

Testing: Prior to delivery to the final integration level ("final" as far as the EDEN ISS contribution is concerned), it shall be verified that all software and software/hardware interaction specifications have been met, that the software especially the software/hardware interaction is failure free and that errors are properly handled. The tests shall be performed as early as possible in the actual EDEN ISS system environment.

3.2 Software Problem Reporting

In the case of any anomaly or problem which is related to EDEN ISS specific software, an adequate problem report/ note shall be written and be communicated to the QM manager.

3.3 Software configuration control

Any EDEN ISS project software will be subject to configuration control. This will be done by:

- Defining configuration items (software components): Configuration accounting by establishing and maintaining actual and previous software releases as part of the project library.

- Establishing a change procedure for processing of non-conformances: Any change shall be clearly indicated and traceable to all affected levels.
- Implementation verification: The EDEN ISS project library (DLR Team site) will keep record of all software revisions which have been used to perform development, qualification and acceptance tests. Separated from the historic part of the library always the actual software versions will be stored as a reference for e.g. tests or inspections.
- Documentation: During the various software development phases (if applicable), the following documents will be generated. The following is a guideline which may be tailored to the needs of the specific sub project:
 - Software operations manual
 - Software verification and validation plan
 - Test documentation.

It cannot be expected that the software engineers who were responsible for the development phase will be available in the operational phase. Therefore, it is indispensable to establish a Software Operation Manual (SOM) which needs to be a living document through the various project phases. The manual needs to give an overview on the software structure, the functions and interfaces of the software modules, an installation procedure for ground software, a history of observed failures and how they have been repaired (NCR's, change requests) and failure messages together with possible solutions.

4 Configuration Management and Control

4.1 General

EDEN ISS deliverables shall be applied in various applications and missions such that the design definition and the traceability of design changes and problems/non-conformances is crucial for the improvement of the design maturity and robustness, especially, that design deficiencies and problems are appropriately recognized and processed.

In order to assure that documentation is generated in a comprehensive, up-to date and cost effective way, EDEN ISS applies configuration control procedures that are outlined in this section. Configuration control is further related to information management to assure that the necessary information is available for each EDEN ISS /project member.

Configuration control shall assure that the development, qualification and manufacturing is documented in a systematic, transparent and concise way and that the delivered hard- and software is compliant with the overall project documents.

The main tools & procedures are:

- Documentation control (Documentation standard, document release, document change control)
- Change control (monthly reports); Depending on the level of change, dedicated meetings with the Technical Board (TB) will be organized
- Dedicated summaries of current design status and list of highlighted changes will be published by the QM responsible person
- Implementation verification (as-built vs. as-designed configuration).

4.2 Confidentiality

The EDEN ISS confidentiality policy is defined in the consortium's Grant Agreement.

4.3 Configuration items

Typical configuration items are:

- Equipment (H/W) and the embedded software
- Documents.

4.4 Documentation control

Formal tools will be effective to assure that the documentation requirements are met and that the documentation objectives are clearly described. Any document will conform to the formal attributes:

- Unique document title
- Approval note (Project manager, technical responsible, QM, Customer (if mutual agreements are affected))

- Document number
- Date, issue, revision
- Document change record (the latest changes are marked by a side bar)
- Distribution listing (only applicable when not for public distribution).

4.5 Document Naming and Enumeration

Documents within the EDEN ISS project are to be named and enumerated according to the following scheme:

<AA>-<BB>-<E.E>-<F.FF>-<Descriptor>-<X.Y>.<ext>

Past the period, the extension <ext> is added to define the file type.

Definition of components of a file name:

<AA>: Project mnemonic, here "EDEN ISS"

<E.E>: Enumeration of work package number.

The work package for which the document is associated should be listed using the presented two digit format. The characters 'WP' are to be included in front of these values.

<F.FF>: Enumeration of deliverable number.

For documents which are deliverables to the EU, the E.EE digits denote deliverable code of the particular document. Thus the deliverable 1.2 would have the two digit code 1.2. Deliverable 3.12 would have the three digit code 3.12. In all cases, these numbers are preceded with the character 'D' to indicate deliverable.

<BB>: Issuing organisation,

Airbus Defense and Space	ADS
Aero Sekur S.p.A.	AS
Alfred-Wegener-Institut	AWI
Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche	CNR
Stichting Dienst Landbouwkundig Onderzoek	DLO
Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V.	DLR
EnginSoft S.p.A.	ES
Heliospectra AB	HS
Limerick Institute of Technology	LIT
LIQUIFER Systems Group GmbH	LSG

Thales Alenia Space Italia S.p.A.	TASI
Telespazio S.p.A.	TPZ
University of Guelph	UoG

<Descriptor>: readable description of content, to be used as far as reasonable.

<X.Y>: **X: Version, Y: Revision. Drafts as 0.n, released documents as 1.n.**

For documents, for which a versioning is not too meaningful (as e.g. protocols) the versioning is optional. In front of the versioning a “v” (not “V”) shall indicate the version.

Examples for naming and enumerating according to the following scheme:

<AA>-<BB>-<E.E>-<F.FF>-<Descriptor>-<X.Y>.<ext>,

are provided as representative examples:

EDEN ISS-DLR-WP1.1-D1.1-Quality management plan-v1.1.docx

Represents an EDEN ISS quality management planning document drafted by DLR, which is the deliverable number 1.1 and represents the first version of the released document.

or

EDEN ISS-HS-WP3.4-D3.9-LS design document-v0.1.docx

Represents an EDEN ISS lighting system design document drafted by Heliospectra which is deliverable number 3.9 and represents a draft of the document.

For Minutes of Meetings (MOM) the date of the meeting shall be given in YYYYMMDD as beginning of descriptor followed by text descriptor with separator (“_” not “-”)

EDEN ISS-DLR-WP3.1_20151206_MOM service section design meeting.docx

Represents an EDEN ISS design meeting on 6th of December 2015, which can be associated with WP 3.1 (Structure) of the project

All documents, which are issued within the EDEN ISS project will be logged by the project management team for reference as well as to coordinate the consistent documentation numbering scheme.

4.6 Change processing

The following change types exist:

- Engineering change proposals
- Waiver requests.

Changes to the approved configuration are only possible after formal approval. Intentional alterations to specifications, drawings, procedures or other types of documents are reflected in Engineering Change Proposals (ECP's). Unforeseen discrepancies between the approved documentation and the actual hard- or software are documented by problem/non-conformance reports (NCR). Deviations from applicable system requirements will be covered by a waiver (request).

An Engineering Change Proposal will contain:

- An identification number
- Date
- Affected configuration item
- Affected document
- Short title
- Change description (in verbal form, by exchange pages or red-marked drawing. Preferred solution: two drawings: “was” and “is”)
- Justification/rationale.

Unexpected/unintended deviations from system requirements will be covered by a Request for Waiver (RfW), containing the following information:

- Project
- A unique identification number
- Title
- Date
- Version
- Affected configuration item
- Affected document(s)
- Description
- Rationale
- Adverse effects
- Approval.

4.7 Implementation Verification

Implementation verification will ensure that the as-designed configuration which is specified in the project library is consistent with the actual hardware and software implementation.

Prior to integration incoming inspections will be performed. The findings will be documented in inspection reports which will become part of the regular progress reports.

Baselines and Design Reviews

Throughout the development of the project, several milestones are identified where the design is assessed and frozen to the extent that further changes must be evaluated prior to incorporation.

These baselines are established and documented as results of the project reviews. Beside the Scientific Advisory Board, suitable review teams will be established, including experts from the participating partners, sub-contractors or industry as required, to ensure a critical view at the project at defined milestones.

References

Not applicable for this document.